
Opportunity Mapping: A Collaborative Approach to Maximizing Research Impact

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Abstract: Industry academia collaboration in large research projects requires working across several boundaries (geographical, disciplinary, academia & industry). An integrated method to facilitate knowledge generation and translation into innovations that are user-relevant, actionable, and have commercial potential is needed. Based on a design-led process we developed and introduced the concept of an “Opportunity Map” as central tool to translate research results into ideas and innovations. The concept is easily transferable to other contexts and is therefore an interesting case study for other researchers and practitioners in the fields of research and innovation management. A case study from SafeConsume, a EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation project with 32 organizations across 14 countries and several disciplines across industry and academia participating is presented. The project aimed at reducing foodborne illnesses and saving lives by changing consumer’s food behavior.

Keywords: opportunity map; design-led innovation; food safety, design thinking; industry-academia collaboration; impact; systemic design, design research; qualitative research; user research; co-creation; facilitation; visualization

1 The challenge of making research results relevant and actionable

Industry academia collaboration in large research projects requires working across several boundaries (geographical, disciplinary, academia & industry). Often large amounts of data and rich insights are generated in such projects which need analysis and sensemaking across actors so they can be used further in the project to spark ideation, creativity and development of solutions that meet user needs. An integrated method to facilitate knowledge generation and translation into innovations that are user-relevant, actionable, and have commercial potential is needed. Based on a design-led process we developed and introduced the concept of “Opportunity Mapping” as central tool to synthesize research results and translate them into ideas and innovations. The concept is easily transferable to other contexts and is therefore an interesting case study for other researchers and practitioners in the fields of research and innovation management.

Bridging the academia-industry gap is essential yet challenging and demands a broader understanding of impact among scholars (Wickert et al., 2021). Funding bodies like the

European Union (EU) and national research councils define the impact of research and innovation projects across four dimensions (EC, 2024):

- *Scientific Impact*: advancements in knowledge and technology.
- *Economic Impact*: economic benefits, such as new products, services, or processes that enhance productivity and competitiveness.
- *Societal Impact*: improvements to society and quality of life (public policy, health, environment, and cultural enrichment).
- *Policy Impact*: influence research has on policy-making and public services.

Beyond a product and technology focus a broader societal and sustainability impact is expected from research projects, such as addressing health issues or food waste through behavioral change. That change can be achieved through education, communication and policy making in addition to providing new products, services, or technologies. Project success in different project environments depends on the project methodology applied (Joslin and Müller, 2016). The choice of project methodology should provide a structured framework that aligns with project goals, ensures consistency, and facilitates effective risk and resource management. Key aspects to consider when selecting or designing a methodology include the project's type and complexity, organizational culture, governance structures, and the need for flexibility and customization. Additionally, methodologies should incorporate robust stakeholder engagement and risk management processes and be adaptable to both internal and external environmental factors. The different approaches to insight creation and solution development of i.e. natural scientists, social scientists, and designers present some challenges but also large opportunities for better project outcome (Gonera and Pabst 2019). 'The natural sciences are concerned with how things are ... design on the other hand is concerned with how things ought to be.' (Simon 1969). Common between design and social sciences is the human-centered approach and the focus on solving real world problems (Frascara, 2002), whereas methodologies differ significantly; creative processes dominate in design while empirical research methods dominate social sciences. Also, the output differs from tangible concepts to knowledge generation and new theories. In the context of multidisciplinary and multi actor research and innovation projects it has been shown that using design thinking as collaborative methodology leads to better collaboration, higher engagement, better communication and more focus on impact and meeting user needs (Veflen and Gonera, 2023). Previous studies have also explored the benefits and barriers of design thinking, highlighting its role in fostering collaboration and impact focus in research projects. However, effectively translating research-based knowledge into industry practices remains a hurdle. Visualizations and prototypes as boundary objects contribute to better cross-disciplinary knowledge sharing, learning, and collaboration in R&I activities (Carraresi et al., 2024). A dynamic framework for assessing and improving decision making in the translation of research and innovation for impact (Scholz et al., 2023) recommends multidimensional assessment tools that help particularly universities to identify promising innovations and transform them into market opportunities. Our work and case study in one large R&I project has developed such a dynamic tool which can be reapplied to other projects and organizations.

2 The role of design for facilitating collaboration, user focus, and innovation

On the one hand, public funding bodies increasingly call for multidisciplinary projects that solve complex societal issues (EU Horizon Europe). Although designers are commonly involved in commercial product development processes, it is still not common to include designer competence in academic research projects lead by natural or social scientists. Only a few studies exist that describe the use of design and design thinking in that respective context (Minder and Heidemann Lassen, 2018; Veflen and Gonera, 2023). We believe there are huge advantages design thinking can bring to research and innovation projects, such as increased user focus, insight generation and visualization, facilitation of collaboration, prioritizing ideation, making research results tangible and engaging, increasing the focus on solutions and innovations (Gonera and Pabst 2019; Micheli et al. 2019; Caccamo, Pittino and Tell 2022). Applying design thinking in innovation projects leads to product concepts with higher feasibility, relevance and specificity compared to traditional approaches (Meinel et al. 2020). Due to reporting requirements, EU projects

usually have a linear project plan with milestones and deliveries in contrast to the iterative nature of design work. This milestone dilemma is described by Hölzle and Rhinow (2019) who point out that unknown learning objectives are hard to plan according to milestones. Design thinking in innovation can be understood as a learning process (Beckman and Barry 2007). This however assumes that learning through design is a clear objective in the respective context. Academic research and innovation projects are often characterized by focus on personal productivity, the search for knowledge and the building of reputation among like-minded people (Simons et al. 2011; Pabst et al. 2020). Also, the innovation process in academically managed projects can be described as incomplete at both ends - user needs are hesitantly included in the innovation process and there is often limited interest in market commercialization (Gonera and Pabst 2019). At the same time these are the underexplored areas which should complement each other eventually (Hölzle and Rhinow, 2019). To counterbalance some of the abovementioned weaknesses, research by design (Morrison and Sevaldson, 2010) embraces and handles complexity, puts rich (qualitative and quantitative) data and insights in a context with the goal to identify opportunities that inspire for action and change. In our case study we applied a research by design and design thinking approach with the ambition to maximize knowledge sharing, collaboration, and research impact.

3 Case description of a large, international, transdisciplinary EU project

Every year there are 23 million cases, and 5000 deaths related to food caused by bacteria, viruses, toxins and allergens in Europe (WHO, 2015). The objective of SafeConsume (<https://safeconsume.eu/>) was to “reduce health burden from foodborne illnesses: changing consumers’ behavior to reduce exposure to hazards and decrease risk through effective and convenient tools and products, communication strategies, education and an inclusive food safety policy”. The top five foodborne hazards in Europe accounting for approximately 70% of the health burdens related to foodborne illnesses were targeted in SafeConsume. Over five years of research new insights, tools and products, communication strategies and education to reduce exposure to hazards and decrease risk of foodborne illnesses were developed and delivered. SafeConsume is built on the hypothesis that consumer behavior is both a core problem and solution. Thus, increasing consumers’ confidence and competence in responsible and safe food handling and consumption will reduce food borne illnesses and deaths. The consortium comprised of 32 participants from 14 countries and consisted of scientists (microbiology, sociology, management, education, and innovation), manufactures, universities, marketing/communication and a design agency (Langsrud, 2022). The project was structured into work packages (WP) with WP1,2,3 generating insights on consumers’ food behavior across 10 countries and the effect of the behaviors on the resulting risks. WP4,5, and 6 developed solutions (tools, technologies, education, communication, policy recommendations) to reduce foodborne illnesses. This two-step R&I approach called for an integrated method to facilitate knowledge generation and translation into innovations that are user-relevant, actionable, and have commercial potential for the industry partners and beyond.

Figure 1: SafeConsume project WP structure

4 Research by design

The aim of including designers into this complex project was to develop a method and assist the translating from natural and social sciences into a form that facilitates the innovation process. Designers supported the research in the consortium with a novel perspective on analyzing, synthesizing and translating user insights (about food safety and kitchen hygiene) into design opportunities. By prioritizing and focusing on some of the behaviors identified by the consortium researchers they facilitated the development of tangible concepts and prototypes to support the project aim of reducing foodborne illnesses through change of behavior triggered by new knowledge, technology, or tools. We describe the approach as research by design where design and research are interconnected, and new knowledge is produced. We aimed at generating desirable, possibly unexpected, perspectives and concepts. Research and design are closely connected but distinct activities. Both are purposeful processes aimed at creating something new (Stappers and Giaccardi, 2017). However, while research focuses on generating new, widely applicable knowledge, design seeks to develop solutions tailored to specific situations. Project participants had different “assigned” roles in this process spanning from theory building and research question set-up, to documenting insights, organizing practicalities and user research, to designing interventions, improving practice and project management as proposed by (Sleeswijk Visser, 2018). Research by design produces verbal, non-verbal and highly visual forms of output and discourse proper to disciplinary practice that make it discussable, accessible and useful to peers and others (Hauberg, 2011; Roggema, 2016). The approach is characterized through its encouragement of the involvement of a wide variety of sources, participants and stakeholders with a consumer-driven food safety strategy. It is a solution-based problem-solving approach that is human-centered and iterative. Leaning on design thinking, we built the ideate, prototype, test and learn steps on the research results, but not only after research activities were completed, but also early, during and late in the research work packages. The approach encourages to generate many ideas for innovative solutions that combine and add to the results from consumer and microbial studies. Another benefit of the design approach is its inherent capability to visualize and structure large amounts of data in complex systems to create accessible and inspiring overviews as boundary objects (Caccamo et al. 2022) which enable common understanding, knowledge exchange and collaboration between experts from different fields.

5 The opportunity map approach

The purpose of the Opportunity Map (OM) is to translate the information found in WPs 1, 2 and 3 into a form suitable for inspired and actionable engagement with the design, research, and innovation communities both inside and outside the project. Figure 2 shows where in the design thinking process the OM is situated and its role as “switchboard” between defining problems and developing actionable innovative solutions.

Figure 2: The opportunity map in SafeConsume illustrated with the double diamond British Design Council, 2024

Starting point for the OM was a Risk Behavior Map (RBM) which is a documentation of all risky consumer behaviors that can lead to food borne illnesses based on observational studies in 7 countries, laboratory experiments simulating consumer behavior, a survey in 10 countries and a risk reduction potential calculation. The OM is a matrix of potential intervention points and defines the space for innovation. It is a means of communication, from the scientific world of social and natural sciences to the world of innovation. The assessment was based on the findings from WPs 1, 2, 3 relating to behaviors, physical conditions encountered in kitchens and food consumption locations, microbiological results, challenges faced by vulnerable groups and barriers to improvement. In the OM, we applied principles from design methodology and lean startup to ensure a more iterative and agile approach where the tasks were run in shorter sprints involving transdisciplinary working teams from all WPs. Qualitative and quantitative consumer risk assessment by microbiologists, social scientists and data scientists across ten countries were discussed and synthesized in several cross-functional workshops. An initial OM was developed and populated with an initial data set from WPs 1, 2, 3 12 months into the project where results from literature reviews and research were discussed and a workshop on opportunity and idea generation was held. After 21 months another large workshop was held across all WPs and actors to discuss and further refine the risk areas. WP4 then developed a Prioritized Risk Area Map where the risks were prioritized across countries and supplemented with further information. The format of the OM was revised in the sense that the OM is now a mirror of the Prioritized Risk Area Map. All partners participated in a workshop in month 24, to validate the opportunity areas and the format of the OM. By that time, an initial quantitative risk ranking was available from the large-scale consumer survey and supported the identified opportunities.

One dimension of the OM are the stages in the consumer journey (Food Choice, Shopping, Transport, Storage, Preparation, Serving, Cleaning, Left-overs and Disposal). The other dimensions of the OM are risky consumer behaviors, consumer motivations, opportunity areas linked to hazards, pathogens, food types, and vulnerable consumer groups. Each of the prioritized risk areas were translated into opportunity areas. Out of many risky consumer behaviors, 21 opportunity areas were prioritized. An opportunity is defined as a “How might we ... “-question (HMW). Using the HMW questions imposes a generative

approach to translating barriers into opportunities which challenges project members to think of actionable solutions (Curedale, 2019; von Thienen et al. 2014). Example of opportunities are “How might we avoid that consumers store eggs at too high temperature?” or “How might we secure safe temperatures in refrigerators?”. The HMW questions also took the meta motivations and attitudes identified by the social scientist into consideration. So there could have been several HMW questions generated for one risk area. The “How might we” generates several possible answers and is a launchpad for specific ideas that can be incorporated in WP4 (Tools and Technologies), WP5 (Communication Strategies), WP6 (Education), and WP7 (Policy). The opportunity map is a prioritization, communication and visualization tool meant to stimulate common understanding, ideation and focus innovation efforts. Right away, idea and concept development in WPs 4, 5, 6 and 7 started and the OM was continuously populated with innovation and intervention ideas for products and technologies, communication, education and policy. Figure 3 illustrates the process described above with its different stages and inputs / outputs.

Figure 3: overall process of developing and using the opportunity map in SafeConsume

The Opportunity Map - important elements and functions

Figure 4 illustrates the translation from an identified risk area into an opportunity area. The risk area contains the insights that elderly as a vulnerable group often eat RTE (ready to eat) food after it has expired and some of the underlying behaviors as well as graphical information about the pathogen, type of food, risk group and risk reduction potential. This information is then transferred into the opportunity area with a HMW question and link to the insights.

Figure 4: Illustration of a risk area identified through a research-based insight process (top image) and the resulting opportunity area (bottom image) as springboard for ideation and innovation.

A project specific user journey was developed as central element and artifact early in the project jointly across disciplines (microbiology, sociology, consumer research, designs). This fostered a discussion on which consumer actions and behaviors are of interest when aiming to reduce the risk for food borne illnesses. The consumer journey has played a pivotal role both in the project and in the OM development. The 21 opportunity areas are aligned along the user journey as intervention points (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: The SafeConsume Opportunity Map (link to high resolution image: [SafeConsume Opportunity Map high res](#))

The Opportunity Map - innovation work and outcome

The visual format of the OM is a tangible presentation of the research-based insights and invites for engagement across the entire project. We both had a digital version but also large printouts for workshops. The format allowed the team to zoom in and out of different levels of detail, i.e. get an overview of project results, follow the risks and opportunities along the user journey or deep dive into one of the opportunity areas, specific pathogens or vulnerable groups. The OM is a valuable tool to navigate complexity in such a large multi-actor project. We had several project workshops based on the OM where teams of project members used the insights and HMW questions to generate a large number of ideas for education, communication, policy and technology innovations. Documentation of one such workshop is shown in Figure 6 and shows the spread of ideas across the OM in Figure 7.

Figure 6: Opportunity map workshop (2019, Porto)

Figure 7: Ideas developed in one project workshop illustrated across the OM

Coming back to industry academia collaboration and the importance of good knowledge transfer and relevancy of research results, the OM was an important tool for engaging the seven companies actively. First of all, the OM was an excellent tool to communicate the complex research-based findings to industry persons who have a) not participated in the research and b) spent relatively little time in the project due to the nature of such projects and the internal priorities in companies. Based on the company's key technologies, consumer group target and future strategy, each company in SafeConsume focused on specific opportunity areas as illustrated in Figure 8. Even though some companies entered the project with a lead technology and a specific innovation goal, they gained a tremendous amount of insights which enabled creativity and prototyping. Visualizing the ownership of the different opportunity areas in the consortium led to commitment from the companies but also allowed a constructive discussion about IPR ownership and exploitation and commercialization strategies. The latter two can often be underestimated in academically led projects and the OM is a valuable tool to create awareness around this issue and to communicate its importance. Discussing and defining the opportunities for and within each company allowed us to ideate more targeted around a problem area and within the company goals without limiting the solution space. Some companies, i.e. IKEA in addition engaged design students from AHO (Architecture and Design School Oslo) to get access to more and more “out of the box” ideas.

Figure 8: Opportunity areas for industry actors in SafeConsume

Out of many ideas and concepts, 23 design concepts of tools or technologies were developed further. Some examples are shown in Figure 9. At this point it is important to note that the educational, policy and communication interventions are not discussed further in this article as the focus is academia – industry knowledge transfer. It is worthwhile highlighting that the OM concept delivered valuable innovations and interventions also for these types of interventions and can thus be applied holistically. The design studio Designit led the design development of most of the concepts and collected and evaluated feedback. The design concepts were illustrated and presented to the project in a way that describes the operating principle, target users, physical construction, the benefits or behavioral requirements for the consumer, how they address the opportunities from the OM and relevant technology. Three main methods for collecting feedback were used: Continuous feedback and concept iterations within the design team and the technology owners, a physical presentation of concepts in Oslo to a core team, and circulation of an online survey to the entire project team. In addition to the prioritized concepts, 85 ideas from SafeConsume were shared publicly in the “book of ideas” (safeconsume.eu/book-of-ideas/). These concepts are prototypes meant for inspiration and sometimes provocation to spur interest and curiosity to develop some of them further and bring them alive to commercial potential.

Figure 9: Selected prototypes developed in SafeConsume based on the OM

6 Methodological and conceptual reflections on maximizing impact

Maximizing impact from research requires a clear focus on impact and implementation already from the planning stage and a deliberate approach is required (Northway et al., 2024). It is important to reference existing frameworks to engage for collaboration; in the case of SafeConsume “Hazard analysis critical control point” (HACCP) from microbiology, “Theory of planned behavior” (TOP) from behavioral science and the “double diamond” from design were applied. As a learning point for future projects, the project could have benefitted from including designer competence even more in the initial phases of gathering insights, bridging gaps between the methodologies used by natural and social scientists and enriching the insights. This could have eased the opportunity mapping process and development of the OM.

Engagement is a precondition to achieving impact. Providing the project team with collaboration tools and creative practices led to engagement with the findings and with other disciplines and created the pathway towards impact in such multidisciplinary research endeavors (Gooch et al., 2017). Also framing questions as we did in the “HMW” approach of the OM leads to constructive and actionable stakeholder engagement. The particular approach of research by design echoes the question of Laursen and Haase (2019) whether non-designers can effectively engage in design practices and processes, or if a designer's expertise is essential to guide the process. In our case study, the involvement of designers and team members with design expertise was crucial. Designers play a key role in fostering collaboration across various disciplines, helping to develop conceptual frameworks (like the OM) that can eventually lead to the creation of prototypes and impact (Aguirre et al., 2017). Over the course of three years design students from AHO additionally contributed with over 100 ideas and prototypes to SafeConsume, which provided a richness of possible solutions to the project team. Design processes are often perceived as chaotic, involving sensemaking activities that integrate diverse insights and ideas from multiple contributors. This dynamic can create tensions, especially with scientists who tend to focus on their specific fields and emphasize precision and detail. Actively assigning and discussing roles in the project may help reduce these tensions (Sleeswijk Visser, 2018). In SafeConsume this was not a huge issue and project internal evaluation showed that the design thinking approach actually led to better knowledge transfer, simplified complex information, improved collaboration and generated a sense of optimism in the project (Veflen and Gonera, 2023). The designer's role to prepare implementation and impact lays in creating acceptance by facilitation a joint identification of problem space and evaluation criteria of ideas and concepts (Minder and Heidemann Lassen, 2019). Finally, it needs to be acknowledged that the described process in a large

research project is very resource intense over a long period of time. This needs to be considered both in budgeting and by allocating resources around key events, i.e. as sprints.

7 Managerial and practical implications

The OM offers a transferable approach that can be applied in different types of projects – commercial innovation work, research projects, organizational changes etc. As any framework, it needs to be adapted to the context and the nature of problems to solve. The OM offers an array of benefits to complex multidisciplinary academia – industry collaboration:

- **Facilitates knowledge generation and translation:** OM helps in systematically analyzing and making sense of large amounts of data and insights generated in research projects, transforming them into innovative ideas and solutions.
- **Enhances collaboration:** By bridging the gap between academia and industry, OM fosters better communication and collaboration among diverse stakeholders, leading to more effective and impactful research outcomes.
- **Supports multidisciplinary integration:** OM accommodates the different approaches of natural scientists, social scientists, and designers, leveraging their unique perspectives to improve project outcomes.
- **Encourages user-centric innovation:** The design-led nature of OM ensures that the innovations developed are closely aligned with user needs, increasing their relevance and potential for real-world application.
- **Improves decision-making:** OM provides a clear framework for evaluating and prioritizing opportunities, aiding in strategic decision-making.
- **Inspires for action and maximizes impact:** By focusing on user-relevant and actionable innovations, OM helps maximize the scientific, economic, societal, and policy impact of research projects

In a classical design process (i.e. double diamond) the OM would be the midpoint. The map can be an end-result to communicate opportunity space for others to work on or it can be a springboard / steppingstone for innovation within a project or an organization to develop solutions for specific challenges/opportunities.

Finally, we have some practical advice to be considered when applying the OM approach:

Ensure progress

- Have a process leader and some clear deadlines (i.e. designer, design innovation catalyst, action researcher (Price et al., 2021))
- Keep track of the large amount of data and insights (database, reports, rich design space, mural or miro boards)
- OM and design materials contribute to show project evolution and progress.

Ensure engagement and creativity

- Be positive, say yes – embrace challenges, have an open mind ...
- Use a “common easy to understand language” that makes it easy for everyone in the team to understand, regardless of discipline, background and language skills.
- Facilitate for frequent dialogues and (inter)action (online, during meetings)
- Communicate frequently to bring in different perspectives, to test out hypothesis, to onboard and engage, to ideate, create and prioritize.
- Encourage and make room for open minded and broad ideation, hold back on evaluation and prioritization until after you have come up with many ideas.
- Visualize insights and ideas to reduce the barrier to engage with the material. Large printouts encourage engagement and support less formal discussions.

Ensure impact

- Involve broadly across all functions and stakeholders
- Work with preliminary solutions to facilitate an open process (Manzini, 2015)
- Develop many solutions
- Prioritize among solutions (according to jointly developed criteria – i.e. relevance for implementation by project partners, health burden risk reduction potential)
- Think “impact” from start

8 Conclusions

The Opportunity Mapping approach presented in this paper demonstrates a robust yet flexible framework for translating research insights into actionable innovations. By integrating design thinking with multidisciplinary collaboration, the OM effectively bridges the gap between academia and industry, fostering user-centric solutions that address complex societal challenges such as foodborne illnesses. The case study from the SafeConsume project highlights the OM's potential to enhance knowledge transfer, facilitate stakeholder engagement, and drive impactful innovations. The findings underscore the importance of iterative, agile methodologies in maximizing research impact and ensuring the relevance of innovations to end-users. In SafeConsume, the OM approach contributed to all four aspects of impact (scientific, economic, societal, and policy) as it was used to advance knowledge, develop interventions for commercial actors, reduce risk of food borne illnesses for consumers, and develop educational material and policy recommendations.

9 Limitations and Further Research

While the OM approach has shown significant promise, there are several limitations and areas for further research. Further research is needed to explore the scalability of the OM approach across different types of projects and organizational contexts. Future research could investigate how the OM can be integrated with other innovation management methodologies to enhance its effectiveness. The impact of stakeholder diversity on the effectiveness of the OM approach warrants further exploration, particularly in terms of cultural and disciplinary differences. Developing quantitative metrics to evaluate the success of the OM in translating research insights into actionable innovations would provide a more robust assessment of its effectiveness.

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